

ENERGY OF THE SOLAR RAYS THROUGH TABLE SALT COLLECTION AND METHODS OF USING THIS ENERGY

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ABSTRACT

The article shows the results of the study of resources of solar energy in Nakhchivan. The amount of solar energy falling on complex mountainous relief area of Autonomous Republic, the energy reserves of solar rays falling on the area were calculated. In mountainous areas, at different heights above sea level, on the slopes of the mountains, the study of the properties of solar rays was carried out, and the conformity of the change of the energy of solar rays depending on the altitude to the law was confirmed. The instability of the energy received from the energy of the sun's rays causes a decrease in the attitude towards the stability and reliability of the energy system. One of the methods of tackling this issue is to utilize a system for collecting and accumulating electric energy. For this purpose, the article shows the results of scientific research conducted on table salt, which is available in the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and has the ability to collect and store the heat energy of the solar rays. New technological methods, which have the highest productivity and require relatively low costs, which can satisfy the needs of independent consumers, are shown, which we recommend to be applied.

Keywords: solar energy, table salt, energy collection, heat energy, energy capacity, heat accumulator.

INTRODUCTION

One of the global problems of humanity is the continuous supply of energy for countries to develop based on their geographical, national and historical characteristics.

The main difference between the production of electricity and any other energy production is the impossibility of storing the electricity produced. The electricity produced is either used for people's needs or lost. It is from this point of view that the issue of storing the produced electricity is attracting more and more attention.

In mountainous areas, it is very expensive for consumers to connect to the centralized electricity supply system. From this point of view, it is considered appropriate to use stationary power plants that are far from centralized power supply systems in mountainous areas and meet the energy needs of consumers.

In this regard, the source of energy that can meet the energy needs of consumers is solar energy, which has an inexhaustible energy reserve, is the most cost-

effective, ecologically clean, and does not pollute the environment.

SOLVING THE PROBLEMS OF CONVERTING THE FLOW OF SUNLIGHT INTO ENERGY

By using solar energy, consumers' energy problems can be solved in a simple and inexpensive way. For this, it is necessary to solve the problems of converting a small part of the energy of the solar rays into other energy.

However, the energy received from solar energy is characterized by its periodicity, and some problems arise here. The sun supplies people with cheap electricity only during the day and no sun in the evening.

Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is located at 39° north latitude and 45° east longitude A ($\varphi^0 = 39^{\circ}$; $\psi^0 = 45^{\circ}$), and the sun's rays coming to its territory have a lot of energy resources [2]. That is why it is interesting to use stationary solar power plants that produce electricity to meet the energy needs of consumers.

(Figure 1.)

Fig. 1. Division of wind energy resources of Nakhchivan MR into zones.

- – less than 3 m/sec;
- – from 3 m/sec. to 6 m/sec.;
- – more than 6 m/sec.

The duration of the solar rays reaching the surface of Nakhchivan located in depression is quite high (2900÷3000 hours) annually. The duration of sunny days is 290–300 hours in March, 300–310 hours in April, 320–330 hours in May, 460 hours in June, 470 hours in July, 470 hours in August, 330–340 hours in September and 320 hours in October.

As you rise above sea level in mountainous areas, the optical layer of the atmosphere decreases, the atmospheric pressure decreases, the efficiency of solar rays increases by 0.007 0.14 kW/m² per 100 meters

In the Autonomous Republic of Nakhchivan, solar energy can be used by converting this energy into heat and electricity. For this purpose, we have calculated the duration of sunny days (T_g) for each day of the 12 months of the year in the area (Table 1):

Table 1

Month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
T_g , hour	9,6	10,57	11,74	13,02	14,13	14,69	14,44	13,48	11,76	10,95	9,8	9,3

Based on the calculations, it was determined that the energy values of the solar rays falling on the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic are equal to 1214 W/m² in the summer months and 567 W/m² in the winter months.

Table 2 shows the maximum \mathcal{E}_h (kWh/m².day) values of the energy of the sun's rays coming to the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic in one day:

Table 2

Ay	The number of days counted, n	T_{day} hour	R_{max} Vt/m ²	\mathcal{E}_h (kVt hour/m ² · day)
I	15	9,6	294,36	1,800
II	45	10,57	459,36	3,092
III	74	11,74	682,44	5,103
IV	105	13,02	900,24	7,466
V	135	14,13	1050,72	9,457
VI	166	14,69	1111,4	10,400
VII	196	14,44	1089,0	10,016
VIII	227	13,48	976,8	8,387
IX	258	11,76	778,8	5,834
X	288	10,95	543,84	3,793
XI	319	9,8	337,92	2,109
XII	349	9,3	242,88	1,438

Figure 1 shows the graph of the change of \mathcal{E}_h by months of the year:

Fig. 2. Change graph of α_h by months of the year.

Solar energy can be converted into thermal, mechanical and electrical energy relatively easily. The technological processes applied during the conversion of solar energy into other energy and its use are very diverse with their technological complexity and differ significantly from each other.

Currently, the most common way to use solar energy is to obtain electricity directly from the sun. The disadvantage of these devices is that they only work on a sunny day when the sky is clear.

Scientific and research works were carried out on table salt, which is available in large quantities in autonomous republic and has an ability to collect and

store heat energy. As a result of our scientific research, we have developed a new technological method of collecting the energy of the sun's rays and turning it into heat energy by means of table salt [1].

There is a large amount of table salt (NaCl) from the "Duzdag" deposit of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. The solar absorption coefficient of table salt is characterized by the ability of the salt to absorb the solar rays falling on the salt [1]. The chemical composition of table salt extracted from the "Duzdag" deposit is as follows (Table 3.);

Table 3

NaCl	CaCl ₂	MgCl ₂	NaSO ₄	CaSO ₄	MgSO ₄	Remainder
95,5	0,04	0,001	0,31	0,5	2,0	1,96

Usually, energy is absorbed or emitted as heat by an object or substance, and this thermal effect depends on the initial and final state of the object or substance. Table salt has the ability to collect the energy of the solar rays in a unique way. We find the value of the absorption coefficient of the solar rays falling on it by table salt using the following formula:

$$\alpha = \frac{\Phi}{\Phi_0}$$

Here: Φ is the price of sunlight falling on table salt;

Φ_0 – solar rays absorbed by table salt.

The specific weight of table salt extracted from the "Duzdag" deposit is 2.165 g/cm³, the melting temperature is 800.8 °C, the boiling temperature is 1465 °C, and the absorption of solar rays by salt crystals is equal to 90%.

Using special parabolic lenses, the energy of the solar rays is directed onto the table salt placed in the tube, the salt is heated and the temperature increases until the table salt melts. In this device, the energy of the solar rays can be collected in the form of heat in table salt and stored in the form of heated salt for a long time (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Collecting and storing the energy of the solar rays by means of table salt.

The amount of heat T (k Coul) collected in table salt is found by the following formula

$$T = m \cdot C_d \cdot (T_2 - T_1)$$

Here: m – mass of table salt, (kg);
 C_d - specific heat capacity of table salt (kCoul / kg °C), C_d=0,88;
 T₁ – is the first temperature of table salt (°C)
 T₂ - is the last temperature of table salt (°C);

Let's determine the amount of heat T collected in table salt with a mass of 1 kg:

T₁– we take the initial temperature of the salt to be +20 °C
 T₂- we take the final temperature of the salt to be + 400 °C

1 kcal or 1.1636 W hour is required to heat 1 kg of table salt to °C. In this case:

It would be $T = 1 \text{ kg} \cdot 0,88 \cdot 380 \text{ } 0\text{C} = 334,4 \text{ kcal} = 389,11 \text{ kW. hour}$

The amount of useful heating power (W_b) of the pipe with table salt is found by the following formula:

$$W_b = R_{gs} \cdot R_b \cdot T \cdot \cos \theta \cdot K_i \cdot K_t$$

Here: R_{gs} – amount of solar rays falling on 1m³ of the pipe – 1214 W/m²

R^b – solar absorption coefficient of table salt , – 0,45 BТ/(M· C⁰)

cos θ the angle of incidence of the solar rays falling on the pipe (0.8);

K_i - heat loss coefficient (0.7);

K_t– is the dusting coefficient of the pipe surface (0.9).

Let's find the amount of useful heating power (W_b) of table salt in a pipe with a diameter of 0.3 meters and a length of 1 meter heated by the solar rays (R_{gsh}) penetrating on the surface of Nakhchivan.

A pipe with a diameter of 0.3 meters and a length of 1 meter is filled with 70.6 kg of table salt. The amount of heat collected in this amount of salt is 27.47 kW. is equal to an hour.

Based on these values, we find the amount of useful heat power (W_b) of the pipe.

$$W_b = 1,214 \text{ kVt} \cdot 0,45 \cdot 389,11 \text{ kVt} \cdot 0,8 \cdot 0,7 \cdot 0,9 = 107,14 \text{ kVt} \cdot \text{hour}$$

Then, the useful heat capacity of the pipe placed on the parabolic lens with a length of 5 meters would be -535.7 kW. an hour.

Thus, it appears from the calculations that by increasing the length of the tube placed on the parabolic lenses, the heating power of table salt can be increased.

For the purpose of ensuring the stability of the users' electrical supplies, a spiral tube is placed inside the table salt collection tube attached to the parabolic lens, and the working gas is injected into the spiral tube. Freon and ammonia gases can be used as working gas (Figure 4):

Fig. 4. Placement of spiral tube inside the tube

In this device, the energy of the solar rays is collected in the form of heat in table salt and stored in the form of heated salt for a long time. The stored heat

can be used to produce electricity and supply heat (Figure 5).

Fig. 5. Schematic of the Solar System
 1- tube filled with table salt; 2- parabolic lens; 3- core;
 4- heat collector; 5- generator; 6- turbine; 7, 8, 9- key valve

The salt is heated by directing the solar rays onto the table salt in the tube (1) placed on the parabolic lens (2). The working gas in the spiral tube placed inside the tube heats up and expands and sets in motion. The gas is directed to the turbine (6) and heat collector (4).

The heated gas drives the turbine (6) and the generator (5) connected to it. At this time, the key valves are open. Excess, unused working gas is collected in the heat collector (4). After the collector (4) is completely filled, the switch valve (8) is closed.

In cloudy weather or for some other reason, if the sun's rays do not fall on the device, the table salt in the tube (1) cools down. At this time, the electricity supply remains stable due to the collected and stored energy. The switch valve (7) is closed and the valve (9) is opened, and the energy collected in the heat collector (4) is transferred to the turbine (6) and converted into electrical energy.

The proposed Solar Plant requires very little funding. The efficiency of capital investment (T) in this facility is found by the following formula:

$$T = \sum T_{kq} / S_{il}$$

Here: S_{il} – annual economic efficiency of the facility

T_{kq} – is the return period of the capital invested in the facility.

The annual economic efficiency of the device (S_{il}) is determined by the following formula:

$$S_{il} = E_{ist} \cdot T_q \cdot \sum \dot{I}_{ist}$$

Here: E_{ist} – the amount of energy supplied to the user

T_q – the value of energy

\dot{I}_{ist} - is the total exploration cost of the facility

Depending on the power of the device, it can provide not only a farm, several small buildings, but

also street lighting. Thus, the collection and storage of energy by this proposed method can be considered the simplest and most promising method of increasing the reliability of the consumer's energy supply [3].

CONCLUSION

The following results were obtained as a result of researching and analyzing the proposed method of collecting and storing cheap energy from the sun using table salt:

1. Cheap table salt produced in the zone of NAR allows efficient use of cheap kinetic energy of the sun.
2. Collecting and storing cheap energy from the sun by means of table salt increases the reliability of supplying users with energy when there is a lack of energy;
3. Collecting and storing cheap energy from the sun by means of table salt prevents critical moments in the energy supply system and ensures efficient operation of the energy system.
4. The area of Nakhchivan has a plenty of solar energy resources. The application of this device, which collects and stores the cheap energy of the sun in this way, can make it possible to achieve great economic results.
5. The use of cheap solar energy is of great importance in the process of protecting ecological conditions and the environment in autonomous republic.

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